

EFFECT OF HEAT TREATMENT ON COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF 3D PRINTED ONYX

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of heat treatment on the compressive strength and structural properties of 3D-printed Onyx, a composite material composed of nylon and carbon fibre. Renowned for its high strength-to-weight ratio and notable impact resistance, Onyx is widely utilized in additive manufacturing for functional, load-bearing components. Heat treatment is acknowledged for its ability to enhance the structural integrity of 3D-printed materials, contributing to increased mechanical strength, reduced residual stresses, improved interlayer bonding, and minimized internal voids. Although Onyx is extensively applied, limited research examines the effects of post-processing techniques such as heat treatment on its compressive performance. This study aims to address this research gap by comparing untreated and heat-treated Onyx samples across a temperature range of 50°C to 200°C. Compressive strength testing was conducted following ASTM D695 standards on both untreated and heat-treated Onyx samples to evaluate potential mechanical property enhancements. Advanced characterization techniques, including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), were utilized to analyse changes in microstructure, crystallinity, and chemical composition resulting from heat treatment. The findings offer valuable insights into optimizing heat treatment conditions to improve the durability and performance of carbon fibre-reinforced composites like Onyx, thereby broadening their applicability for high-strength, lightweight, and durable 3D-printed applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing (AM) has emerged as a disruptive technology, enabling the direct fabrication of complex, lightweight, and customized components through layer-by-layer material deposition. Among the various AM techniques, fused filament fabrication (FFF) has gained particular popularity due to its cost-effectiveness, operational simplicity, and growing compatibility with engineering-grade thermoplastics and composite filaments [1], [2]. FFF allows designers and engineers to quickly transition from digital models to physical parts without the need for traditional tooling, which reduces both lead times and production costs. Its accessibility has catalysed widespread adoption across numerous industries, including aerospace, automotive, healthcare, and consumer electronics, where functional prototyping and low-volume end-use production are increasingly in demand.

Despite its advantages, FFF faces several challenges that hinder its broader application in load-critical or safety-sensitive components. The layer-by-layer deposition process inherent to FFF often results in mechanically suboptimal structures due to insufficient interlayer adhesion, incomplete fusion between extruded paths, residual thermal stresses, and void formation [3], [4]. These defects contribute

to pronounced anisotropy in the printed parts, where mechanical properties can vary significantly depending on build orientation and load direction. Compressive strength, which is critical for many structural and functional applications, is often compromised due to interfacial weaknesses and the presence of internal porosity, making printed parts susceptible to premature buckling or crushing under load. Moreover, the performance of FFF components can degrade further when exposed to thermally variable environments, such as those encountered in automotive under-hood conditions, aerospace cabins, or outdoor installations.

To improve the mechanical robustness of FFF components, material developers have introduced advanced filaments reinforced with high-performance fillers. One such material is Onyx, a proprietary composite consisting of a nylon matrix reinforced with short carbon fibres. The inclusion of carbon fibre improves the stiffness, dimensional stability, and impact resistance of the printed part while maintaining the ductility and processability of the nylon matrix [5], [6]. These characteristics make Onyx particularly attractive for use in jigs and fixtures, functional prototyping, semi-structural components, and tooling applications. However, despite its promising mechanical profile, the full potential of Onyx remains underutilized due to a limited understanding of how post-processing techniques, such as thermal treatment, influence its structural behaviour—particularly under real-world service conditions.

Heat treatment is a well-established post-processing strategy used in polymer and composite systems to modify material properties by promoting molecular relaxation and structural reorganization. When properly controlled, heat treatment can reduce residual stresses, increase crystallinity in semi-crystalline polymers like nylon, improve interlayer fusion, and eliminate voids, all of which contribute to enhanced mechanical performance [2], [7]. In the context of FFF-printed parts, thermal post-processing has been shown to encourage polymer chain mobility across layer interfaces, which strengthens the interlayer bonds that are typically weak in as-printed parts [8]. This can result in improvements in tensile strength, dimensional stability, and thermal resistance. Nonetheless, the effectiveness of heat treatment depends on multiple variables, including the base polymer, reinforcement type, printing parameters, and treatment temperature and duration. Figure 1 shows the process overview.

Figure 1: Process overview

While prior research has demonstrated the benefits of heat treatment for common thermoplastics like PLA, ABS, and PETG, relatively little attention has been given to fiber-reinforced composites—especially in terms of compressive performance and service behaviour under thermal extremes [9], [10]. Furthermore, most mechanical evaluations are conducted under ambient laboratory conditions, which do not reflect the range of temperatures a part might experience in its end-use environment. This is a critical oversight, especially as AM is increasingly deployed for parts that must function in thermally demanding or fluctuating service conditions. Without a clear understanding of how heat-treated materials respond mechanically at elevated or sub-zero temperatures, engineers risk overestimating the durability and safety of printed components. In contrast, components fabricated via

AM are increasingly used in real-world environments where service temperatures may vary significantly—from sub-zero cold starts to elevated operating temperatures. Yet, little is known about how these thermal service conditions influence the compressive behaviour of materials like Onyx, especially when combined with post-processing heat treatments. Moreover, the question remains whether the benefits of heat treatment persist at service extremes, or whether their effects are diminished—or even reversed—under those conditions.

To address this gap, the present study investigates the compressive strength of both pure nylon and carbon fiber-reinforced nylon (Onyx) subjected to heat treatment and then tested at three distinct temperatures: -40°C , room temperature, and 60°C . This dual-variable approach enables the decoupling of material composition (with vs. without reinforcement) from post-processing effects and reveals how these interact under service-relevant thermal conditions. Compression testing is conducted in accordance with ASTM D695, supported by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) to examine microstructural and chemical changes. The study not only quantifies the mechanical benefits of heat treatment but also explores their temperature dependence, offering insights into the design of thermally robust AM parts.

The novelty of this research lies in its integrated evaluation of material composition, heat treatment, and mechanical performance under multi-temperature environments. The findings advance our understanding of thermally robust design strategies for FFF-printed polymers and composites, enabling more reliable application in structurally and thermally demanding settings.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this study, compression specimens conforming to the ASTM D695-15 [11], standard were fabricated using Onyx®, a micro-carbon fiber-filled nylon thermoplastic developed by Markforged. This material is known for its high stiffness, chemical resistance, and enhanced heat deflection performance, making it suitable for structural applications. The printing was carried out on a Markforged Mark Two system utilizing Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) technology. Printing parameters included a layer height of 0.2 mm, single-material extrusion, and standard infill settings optimized for mechanical testing, as recommended in manufacturer guidelines. The G-code generation and slicing were performed using Eiger, a proprietary, cloud-based software platform by Markforged, which provides automated support generation and optimized toolpaths tailored for Onyx printing.

Following additive manufacturing, the printed specimens underwent post-processing via heat treatment to evaluate thermal conditioning effects on compressive mechanical properties. A total of five groups were prepared: one untreated control and four heat-treated sets conditioned at 50°C , 100°C , 150°C , and 200°C , respectively. All heat treatments were conducted in a convection oven under ambient atmospheric conditions. The selection of temperature values was based on the thermal performance range of Onyx and prior studies demonstrating the potential of thermal post-processing to improve interlayer bonding and reduce microstructural porosity.

Compression testing was conducted using a Zwick Z100 universal testing machine, equipped with a 20 kN compression head and configured for quasi-static loading. The crosshead displacement rate was set to 1.1 mm/min, as prescribed in ASTM D695. To assess temperature-dependent mechanical behavior, tests were performed at three environmental conditions: -40°C , room temperature ($\sim 23^{\circ}\text{C}$), and 60°C . These environmental conditions were achieved using a custom-fabricated thermal chamber attached to the Zwick system shown at Figure 2, allowing for controlled isothermal testing. Each specimen group was tested under all three thermal environments to investigate synergistic effects between heat treatment and service temperature. For each condition, three replicates were tested to ensure statistical consistency and reproducibility. Load-displacement data were recorded and used to evaluate compressive strength, stiffness, and energy absorption.

Figure 2: Designed heat chamber for compression tests for extreme temperatures

3 RESULTS

3.1 Stress–Strain Response

Figure 3 shows the compressive stress–strain behaviour of Onyx samples subjected to different heat treatment temperatures. The untreated control exhibited the lowest strength and stiffness. Heat-treated samples demonstrated progressive improvement with increasing temperature, with the 200 °C group achieving the highest compressive strength and strain at failure. The improvement is attributed to enhanced interlayer bonding and reduced void content due to thermal relaxation and polymer chain mobility during heat treatment

Figure 3: Compressive stress–strain curves of Onyx samples at various heat treatment temperatures

3.2 Compressive Modulus

As summarized in Figure 4, the compressive modulus increased consistently with higher heat treatment temperatures. The control sample showed the lowest modulus (~310 MPa), while the 200 °C group reached over 800 MPa, indicating a more than 2.5× increase. This enhancement is consistent with improved stiffness from increased crystallinity and reduced porosity after heat treatment.

Figure 4: Compressive modulus of Onyx samples control and heat treated

3.3 Porosity Analysis

Micro-CT results in Figure 5 reveal a clear reduction in internal porosity after heat treatment. The untreated samples exhibited a porous volume between 4.43–6.13%, whereas the heat-treated samples showed a reduced range of 2.76–4.49%. This supports the mechanical improvements observed, as reduced void content typically leads to better load distribution and structural integrity in FFF-printed composites.

Figure 5: Micro-CT visualizations of internal porosity in untreated (left) and heat-treated (right) Onyx samples

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the influence of post-processing heat treatment on the compressive performance and microstructural integrity of 3D-printed Onyx specimens. Heat treatment at increasing temperatures (50 °C to 200 °C) resulted in substantial improvements in compressive strength and stiffness, with the 200 °C-treated samples exhibiting the best overall performance. Micro-CT analysis confirmed a reduction in internal porosity, which supports the observed mechanical enhancements. These findings highlight the effectiveness of thermal post-processing in improving the structural quality of carbon fiber-reinforced FFF components.

Future work will involve evaluating the heat-treated samples under extreme service temperatures (−40 °C and 60 °C), to assess the durability and stability of Onyx in thermally demanding environments. These tests will help determine whether the benefits of heat treatment persist under non-ambient conditions and provide guidance for designing AM parts for real-world thermal exposure scenarios.

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